

Editorial

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Face Recognition-based Intelligent System for Effective Students' Class Attendance (FARBSAS)

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Abstract: Students' class attendance is considered very important in many higher institutions of learning. However, some institutions' current system for determining students' attendance has certain loopholes. The current system enables the practice of impersonation, does not curb lateness to class effectively and the present attendance model is not designed to capture attendance in the real sense of it. This article aims to provide a solution to the identified problems by proposing an effective student class attendance system using a prototype called Facial Recognition-Based Students' Attendance System (FARBSAS). Face recognition technology is a type of biometric technology that is emerging in the modern world. The method used to gather data includes a survey to determine students' and lecturers' views of the current attendance system. A survey conducted on 45 students and 11 lecturers from the Department of Computer Science, University of Ibadan (UI) shows that there is a need to change the existing students' class attendance model.

Key Words: Attendance model, facial recognition, biometrics

I. INTRODUCTION

"Attendance is usually considered to reflect students' level of engagement with their course and to be critical to student success..." says Moores *et al.* (2019). Basically this 'engagement with course' is done when students are physically present during a class session to learn. Some lecturers ensure that the students write their names and details on a sheet of paper that must be passed around for the students to provide proof that they were physically present in the class. Sutabri *et al.* (2019) described this pen-and-paper method of conducting the student attendance system in Indonesia that is similar to what is being done in many universities in Nigeria and India (Patel & Priya, 2014). In fact, the physical presence of students in the class had been considered so important that a lecturer quoted what a student wrote saying: "As long as you don't fall asleep, you will be alright" (Dirk, 2010). But we need to readjust this thinking because there is a big difference between being physically present in the class and being actively present in the class.

Fagbenle and Elegbeleye (2014) referred to the definition of attendance as "...not merely being bodily present but including actual participation in the work and activities of the school". This definition clearly defines attendance in a way that captures the purpose of students' attendance in the real sense. To fulfil the purpose of class attendance for students, being physically present is only the beginning of the process. When the combination of students' physical presence and their participation in the class had been recorded, then students' attendance had been taken. After all the actual essence of being in the class is to acquire knowledge and

understanding. Students that practice this type of attendance are the ones that can transform acquired knowledge into solutions which can be scientifically, technically and effectively used to transform society. This is what class attendance should constitute.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Some have the view that a compulsory attendance policy in higher institutions is not the way to go. St. Clair (1999) holds a position against class attendance based on factors that she built on Pintrich's theoretical model of motivation. The position is that, while many have provided some methods of constructing empirical results in finding out whether class attendance has a positive impact on student performance or not, and have largely favoured the conclusion that it does, they did not factor in the importance of student motivation in determining their results. Büchele (2021) also alludes to the fact that prevalent findings and results show that there is a positive correlation between students' class attendance and performance. However, he also holds a contrary view. He says that these findings are usually poorly conducted and would be considered to have been based on weak grounds. Yet on a positive note, he concluded by mentioning that "cognitive engagement partly and behavioural engagement fully mediated the link between attendance and performance". In a nutshell, while motivation needs to be considered as St. Clair pointed out, and cognitive engagement of the students and their behavioural engagement are important as postulated by Büchele, it can only be said that the importance of student's attendance has not been ruled out completely. Quite frankly, the argument does not seem to be about students' attendance, as much as it reflects a stand against administrative policies that demand students' attendance, and in some instances, even grade students based on their attendance performance. So, should the school administration make student attendance compulsory?

Moores *et al.* (2019) provided what can be called an all-angle perspective on various given answers. While some have the opinion that compulsory policies asserted by school administration need not be enforced, with their points raised, the irresistible and irrevocable positions of writers who favour the idea that school authority should make student attendance compulsory are too germane that they cannot be denied.

If one thinks about it, what is the point of the class timetable, if students are not expected to be in the class? What is the point of having class-based schools, if students do not come to class but only show up on the examination day and they eventually have high scores? What is the point of school in which students can learn by themselves and teach themselves by themselves? What is the point of paying school fees or

funding education if students can do as they like without any proper administrative policy on their class attendance? What is the point of graduating students based on character and academic performance when the only way to determine their cognitive strength is by the examination they passed? Is school all about passing examinations? Obviously, the main reason why there is various divergence of opinions anchors on the current understanding of class attendance that focuses mainly on students' physical presence in the class. This forms a major reason why our current understanding of school attendance needs to be modified and properly aligned with the current reality.

A. Related Works

The reality is that many academic projects and works of literature are giving attention to the deployment of biometrics as a way to improve the management of students' attendance systems. In fact, various designs and developments of software had been done. In Nigeria, Okokpujie *et al.* (2017) developed a biometric attendance system using iris recognition technology for student attendance. The main aim is to eliminate the issues of forgery and impersonation. A very good part is that it is a web-based application. Isinkaye *et al.* (2020) developed an Android-based face recognition system for attendance and malpractice control. Their focus was to curtail examination malpractices as it also checks whether a student's attendance record qualifies him or her to sit for the examination. In India, Verma and Gupta (2013) developed a fingerprint-based recognition technology for the student attendance system. This requires the use of an external device called a fingerprint scanner as well the use of a mobile phone to allow parents to monitor the attendance activities of the students. In China, some students also developed a voice recognition-based system for student attendance (Uddin *et al.*, 2016). One good aspect of their work was that they integrated the lecturer's interface into the system. Sunaryono *et al.* (2021) also developed a face recognition-based attendance system in which the students can use their Android

smartphones to connect to the school Wi-Fi in an intranet system. The purpose was to ensure that students who are not on campus will not be able to forge attendance and they allow for quick response (QR) codes generation in addition to their face recognition system.

Quite notably, all the aforementioned projects are good works. However, they have their main focus on the physical presence of students in the class. It is important to understand that the main crux of the issue is not just the management of the physical presence of the students in class. The implementation of an attendance system that will recognize the amalgamation of the physical presence of the students and their class activities as attendance is the way to go. This is the focus of this article.

The choice of using a face recognition system instead of the other options mentioned earlier is based on the considerations that it is less costly to implement (Kawaguchi *et al.*, 2005), convenient to use for the students and face detection can be done from a distance. In a simple description, face recognition is based on computer vision technology whereby facial features are analysed for identification. Basically, three important actions must be taken by the computer: face detection, feature extraction and face recognition matching in the database.

III. METHODOLOGY

A survey was conducted among 45 students and 11 lecturers in the Department of Computer Science at the University of Ibadan (UI) to determine their view of the current pen and paper-based students' attendance system and their view of the adoption of the use of face-based recognition technology instead. The survey was done by issuing a questionnaire to the participants through an online Google document. The questions asked and the result of the survey is as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Responses from 45 Students and 11 Lecturers at the University of Ibadan towards the current attendance system and adoption of a face-based recognition system for attendance

QUESTIONS	YES	NO
Do you consider the pen-and-paper method of taking class attendance as effective or outdated?	60% say Outdated	40% say Effective
Do you consider the percentage of a student's class attendance as an effective measure to determine a student's level of understanding of a course and the ability to transfer the acquired knowledge into the solution domain?	20%	80 %
Do you think that an attendance system that incorporates scores for a student that attended a class and stayed in the class all through can be called an effective class attendance system?	55.6%	44.4%
Do you think that an attendance system that incorporates features like class performance, short presentations, group work or product development can boost students' sense of value for the course of study?	100%	0%
Do you think that an attendance system that awards scores for class participation, presentation, group work or product development can demonstrate a reason to conclude that no student will fail the course as long they are active in class?	66.7%	33.3%
Do you think that using software that can capture your face to take class attendance for you is an effective model or undesirable model?	80%	20%

The result of the survey shows that there is a need to change the way the attendance system is currently being conducted in some higher institutions. There is a need to redefine attendance and instead of continuing the archaic pen-and-paper attendance system, the emergence of biometric technology can provide a better approach to the exercise.

As discussed by Abdulrahman and Alhayani (2023), biometric technologies are gaining popularity in various human endeavours as a way to do human identification and verification by deploying the technology in many ways. Some of these ways include iris recognition, fingerprint recognition, face recognition, and signature, among others. Abdulrahman and Alhayani write further that “face recognition can be considered as a standout amidst the most fruitful biometric discernible verification methods ...”. This expression forms a major factor that influenced the choice of selecting face recognition technology for this study to conduct students’ attendance system.

The article uses the Use Case diagram to provide a system design to explain the features of the proposed face recognition software. An activities diagram is also used to present the flow of actions and activities within the proposed attendance model. The desktop software version of the face recognition software prototype called FARBSAS was developed using Swing in Java programming language,

OpenCV library for face recognition technology and MySQL Workbench 8.0 for relational database management system. OpenCV is a large open-source library that is used for image processing, computer vision, and machine learning.

IV. RESULT

A digital system that can use facial recognition technology to take class attendance for students and track their performance in class is here proposed. The software application is called FARBSAS (Face Recognition-Based Software for Student Attendance System). It would be installed on students’ smartphones or computers or tablets. The students will launch the application when they enter a class, input their access details, select the course code from the menu option, click on the “Attendance” button and the camera of the phone or computer must be actively on until the end of the class session. When the class is over, the application can be stopped, and the attendance for a particular course on a particular day would be recorded. The student can save the feedback in printable formats.

The Activity Diagram in Figure 1 shows how the FARBSAS app that is developed for the students is designed to carry out a series of actions. The Use Case diagram in Figure 2 also shows how the students will interact with the FARBSAS app designed for them.

Figure 1: Activity Diagram showing the activities and actions that would be performed by FARBSAS

Figure 2: Use Case Diagram showing how the student will use the features of FARBSAS

A. Structure of FARBSAS Network

FARBSAS is structured in a way that allows the lecturer and students to interface through their smart devices for attendance-taking. Firstly, the lecturers have their separate graphical user interface (GUI) where they will start a server, a simple server socket, that will listen on protocols for clients to be attached to it. Clients in this instance refer to the students' devices. So, when the students start their GUI, they will select the Attendance button from their application's Main Menu. This will trigger Login GUI. After the students input their Matriculation Numbers and Password, then the student device can connect to the lecturer's server. The lecturer will be able to see all connected devices. This first stage of FARBSAS operation is entirely based on Network architecture as described in Figure 3 below. Of course, there is also database connectivity at the student login menu as can be seen in Figure 6. This means that FARBSAS had already

provided a section where students can register their details and capture their faces. You will see this Register GUI section in Figure 9.

B. Graphical User Interfaces for FARBSAS

Figure 4 shows that the lecturers will start the server on their smart electronic devices. This will allow students to connect. The students will simply need to start FARBSAS on their smart devices, and then select the Attendance button from the main menu as shown in Figure 5. Students will then input their Matric Number and password as shown in Figure 6. If the matric number and password provided are correct, then the Attendance Form in Figure 7 will come up for the student to use face recognition to capture attendance. If the details provided by the student are not correct or one of the details is not correct, the Login Error Page (Figure 8) alert will come out.

Figure 3: Network architecture between lecturer and student

Figure 4: Lecturer's interface to allow students to connect to the class and give scores to students' performance in class

The Attendance Form page (Figure 10) is the page where the student will take their attendance. Basically, this page will allow the student to select the course code that he or she is attending at the moment. Then the name of the student and the matric number as well as the date will come up automatically. The additional features that make the FARBSAS attendance system an effective model are the portions of the form where the student will indicate class performance and the lecturer will award a score. The student's attendance quality will also be tracked by ensuring that once a student's device is a distance away from the specified location coordinates set by the lecturer for all connected devices, the Leave class check box will automatically indicate a mark and the time the student leaves the class will show. If the student stays all through the class, the FARBSAS can determine this since the student's device was connected to the lecturer's set by location distance. When the class is over, the student can select Save Attendance to end the attendance process for the class. The attendance form also allows the students to indicate what they did in the class and the lecturer's score for the performance will show immediately.

Figure 5: FARBSAS Menu Page

Figure 6: FARBSAS Login Page

Figure 7: Attendance Form page

Remember that on the Login page, Figure 6, when a student types in his/her details and either one of the two options provided is wrong or the two options are wrong, then the Login Error page (Figure 8) will show up. If the student is sure that he/she had already registered, the Back button can be used to go back to the Login page to re-enter the correct details. However, if the student is only using the FARBSAS for the first time, the Menu button will allow the student to call the Registration form (Figure 9) page to able to register. When a student selects the Register button on the Login page (Figure 5), the Registration Form (Figure 9) will appear. This is the page where a student can register personal details. Then the student will select the place his face to be close to the

camera.

Figure 8: FARBSAS Login Error Page

Figure 9: FARBSAS Registration page

The Capture Face area on the Figure 9 page is the area where the student will do face capturing. The camera will turn on and a rectangular shape will appear on the face of the student on the Capture Face page. When the student selects the Capture button, the Capture Face page will count the number of grey pictures that were captured. The FARBSAS is

programmed to count 25 grey pictures. The counting will show up in the area where 00 is written. After 25 counts, the face capturing will take effect and all the details of the students that were provided in the Registration Page (Figure 9) will be saved into the database along with the face.

Figure 10: Output for a student's class performance

Figure 11: Three major actions to achieve effective students attendance

Figure 10 shows how to capture a student's class performance beyond being merely physically present in the class. This output will capture what a student did in the class; it could be an oral presentation of a project or assignment or group presentation that needs to be defended in the class, and it could also be actual project work that the lecturer required the students to carry out and any other activities that were

idealized to ensure that students participate while they attended class. The lecturer can award a score for each attribute of the student. Some of the attributes of the student could be the ability to explain the subject, good writing skills, neat presentation and even the ability to implement concepts into products as they may relate to the course of study.

Students can see the output per class session and be able to develop anticipation for success. The scores awarded for each class will help a student to have feedback on areas for improvement and areas of strength. This can even help in developing interest in certain skills that a student may eventually turn into an economic development of the society.

V. DISCUSSION

Based on the result of the survey carried out in Table 1, it can be deduced that there is a need to carry out three important activities which will lead to a complete paradigm shift in the way we currently conduct student attendance. Figure 11 gives a summary of the proposed activities that can produce an effective student attendance paradigm shift. Redefining our current understanding of student attendance will help to shift focus beyond our present views that had been fixated only on the physical presence of students in the classroom. Indeed, defining attendance in a way that includes students' physical presence and their class performances during a class session will reflect the purpose of learning and reposition the educational system in the light of being the productive institution that they are supposed to be.

Monitoring and scoring attendance will also provide a motivational factor for students to realize the value of the institutional policy regarding attendance regulations. The scoring of attendance will boost the participatory level of students in the classes. As FARBSAS has shown, a student who failed to attend a class, or left the class uncompleted for frivolous reasons can readily assess and accept the consequences of such actions. FARBSAS also shows that it is important to redesign students' participation in such a way that the abilities of students will manifest, earn them progress and be nurtured. By this, a student who is gifted in oral presentation can grow their ability, those that are stunning in writing skills will also grow their gift, other students who may be very good in the practice can demonstrate their own and others who may be very good in answering questions in the examinations can also grow their abilities. This is very important because people have various abilities. Hence an attendance system that put these peculiarities into consideration will reduce the failure rate and may even reduce out-of-school issues in society. Using technology to drive these initiatives will take away the pen-and-paper process that is slow, boring and even archaic. One of the best-known technologies is the use of a face recognition system.

VI. CONCLUSION

An attendance system that goes beyond focusing on physical presence is needed for students' attendance. Hence, the amalgamation of physical presence and the class work that students are expected to do, are the combinations that form effective class attendance. It is only when a student does not fulfil this kind of attendance system that it can be concluded that the student is not teachable and so cannot be considered to sit for the examination. This paradigm shift can do more good in attaining the overall purpose of the educational system so that more employable and capable problem-solving students would be produced in higher institutions of the modern age.

Of course, there will be a need to review the ratio of lecturers to students. This is important because, in a situation where a lecturer is teaching a large number of students, it would be

difficult or unrealistic to expect a quality attendance system. But when attention is given to a proper proportion of students by a lecturer, excellent output can be achieved.

It is also important to ensure that there are ports where students would be able to charge their smart electronic devices. FARBSAS can still be scaled up to include features whereby lecturers can load questions for students as assignments, create groups for students to assign short works to them and award scores for students at a later time other than class period to allow for flexibility and ease of labour for them.

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